

Feasibility study of SmallSat autonomous optical navigation in deep space with commercial DSLR sensors by beacon asteroid detection

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Abstract

The focus of this study is the feasibility of employing a commercial camera sensor as the autonomous optical navigation sub-system of a SmallSat on a deep space mission. For this analysis, a standard calibration procedure for a Canon EOS 6D Mark II camera was carried out by acquiring bias, dark, and flat-field frames, and experimenting with a range of exposure times and ISO settings. An attempt was made to understand and characterize the role of sensor temperature, which cannot be controlled in typical consumer camera systems. As a first step towards providing proof of concept for a future system deployable in a space environment and to advance the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of our demonstration, we investigated techniques allowing image acquisition without human interaction with the setup. This included software development to execute a transition from the use of the DigicamControl photography management program to cFS Basecamp, a lightweight environment designed to learn the full NASA core Flight System (cFS) and create app-based solutions, running on Linux. Additionally, automated beacon asteroid detection and autonomous observer position calculation were studied by implementing a dedicated Python program leveraging the Astrometry.net service and running locally, also under Linux.

1. Introduction

The number of deep space missions has grown exponentially over the past decade, serving multiple purposes, including commercial, institutional, and academic objectives. In these missions, SmallSats - which offer advantages such as low cost and rapid development - now have a major part not only in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) but also in deep space exploration (Yıldır, 2024b). However, navigation in the missions still depends on the Deep Space Network (DSN), which has several disadvantages. Since all spacecraft are required to use the same DSN, congestion occurs, and the delays caused by signals traveling between deep space and Earth makes real-time navigation impossible. Additionally, traditional deep space navigation cameras and star trackers require space-grade hardware that is expensive, heavy, and bulky, making them unsuitable for the budgets and sizes of SmallSats (Yıldır, 2024a). These two main issues make autonomous, low-cost onboard navigation a necessity.

Optical autonomous navigation is not a completely new concept. As early as 2000's The Deep Space 1 mission proved that onboard optical navigation is possible for interplanetary travels (Riedel et al., 2000). However, these systems are not suitable for SmallSats as mentioned before. Using Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) cameras, such as DSLR-type cameras (Digital Single Lens Reflex), for deep-space optical navigation has not been explored much. In particular, the impact of uncontrollable variables like sensor temperature on performance has not been systematically investigated in the context of SmallSats. This gap is the main motivation behind this study.

The picture consists of a rectangular array of pixels, each of which contains a DN (digital number) value that ideally is linearly proportional to the number of photons impinging upon a corresponding rectangular region of the detector. The picture may therefore contain images of stars, natural bodies, or even other spacecraft (Owen Jr, 2024). Even a small error in a pixel can cause unreliable results. To prevent that issue, calibration of any sensor is necessary.

In the future, the implementation of an autonomous optical navigation system is going to be done for a CubeSat. The sensor of the Canon EOS 6D Mark II is suitable for our mission due to its mass and size. In this paper, our aim is to prove that commercial cameras can be used as a scientific instrument. To be able to prove that astrometric calibration was studied on the Canon EOS 6D Mark II. For that purpose, dark, bias, and flat frames were studied with light frames.

2. Methodology

Figure 1. Image Acquisition Workflow

The workflow for this study is shown in Figure 1.

Image calibration was performed using bias, dark, and flat frames to reduce noise and aberrations in the captured raw images. Calibrated images were stacked by using DeepSkyStacker (DSS) to highlight faint objects. Then, source detection was performed to identify visible targets. The selected star field was analyzed using plate solving with Astrometry.net. Finally, the relationship between the pixel coordinates in the image and the celestial coordinates was established.

2.1 Observation Setup

The Canon EOS 6D Mark II is a complex instrument made of electronic and mechanical parts (Busch, 2017). Due to the fact that the camera is battery-powered, problems with the power supply could influence the image acquisition during long observation periods. For instance, battery depletion may result in the loss of captured data, while insufficient battery charge may prevent image acquisition entirely. To minimize the risk of such interruptions, an external dummy battery was used throughout the experiments.

In the camera, the Bulb mode is selected. In Bulb mode, the shutter stays open as long as you hold down

the shutter button completely and closes when you let go of the shutter button. This photographic technique is called “bulb exposure” (Canon Inc., 2020). Bulb mode is chosen because of the freedom it provides in the settings; this allows the exposure time to be manually adjusted according to sky conditions.

All images are saved as RAW. The reason to save images in RAW format is to get the exact quality of the taken image without any compression.

Before starting the observation, the camera and computer connection are made using a transfer cable. DigiCamControl software is used for taking any frame. The computer connection aims to prevent any vibration caused by human interaction.

A relatively elevated location was chosen, allowing for visibility as far as possible above the city lights, and the observations took place there.

The setup for the light image acquisition is shown in Figure 2. The camera is aimed at the target celestial object by hand, but the image-taking process is done with a computer connection.

Figure 2. Light Frame Acquisition with two of the authors.

Initially, light frames were taken. These frames include the potential target asteroid signal and stellar background and are used to establish and detect the astrometric navigation line. Required adjustments are made to the light frames by monitoring the real-time sky conditions. To adjust settings, some experimental shots were taken with different ISO values or exposure times. When the most suitable settings were found, between 30 and 100 photographs were taken.

To test the method presented in this paper, the (7) Iris asteroid has been chosen as the target.

2.2 DigiCamControl: Image Capture System

A commercial DSLR camera can be remotely operated from a computer via a USB cable using the open-source camera control program DigiCamControl. This software allows for changing camera settings, pressing the shutter button without physical intervention, and transferring captured images to the computer. In short, photos are taken without human contact, thus preventing any shaking or vibration. In addition to automatic image capture, features such as time-lapse mode are also supported.

Figure 3. DigiCamControl System Architecture

The software provides features such as remote camera control, automatic image capture, manual exposure/ISO settings, time-lapse mode, easy connection via computer, and automatic data transfer when the camera is connected to a computer.

Manually activating the shutter release may cause physical errors in the captured image. Therefore, controlling the camera shutter release remotely and transferring captured images to the computer make the program suitable for use in the pipeline. In addition, being an open-source program opens up possibilities for modification to develop an autonomous deep space imaging system.

Figure 4. DigiCamControl Setup via Computer.

Figure 4 shows how the DigiCamControl software connects the Canon EOS 6D Mark II DSLR camera to the host computer using a TetherPro USB 2.0 to Mini-B 5-Pin cable.

Figure 5. DigiCamControl software screen view.

The screen layout of the software DigiCamControl can be seen in Figure 5.

2.3 Calibration Images

Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) cameras can be considered a breakthrough in astronomy.

Raw, unprocessed images captured with CCD cameras contain noise. These raw images require calibration. This calibration process alters the level of noise in the raw images.

Calibration is performed for dark frames, bias frames, and flat area frames, resulting from the behavior of pixel frames at each temperature and exposure time (Rest, 1996).

Sensor calibration is the most important factor for scientific image acquisition. Photographs processed without calibration frames will contain unwanted errors and noise that reduce data accuracy and quality. The importance of sensor calibration is already explained in detail in the introduction. Calibration mainly consists of three components: dark frames, bias frames, and flat frames.

2.3.1. Calibration Image Acquisition

The main reason for calibrating RAW DSLR images is to identify sensor-related errors and remove them using calibration frames. Examples of said errors include thermal noise, hot pixels, lens distortion, and pixel-to-pixel sensitivity differences.

2.3.1.1. Dark Frames

A CCD's (Charged-Coupled Device) pixels will acquire a signal proportionate to the exposure time even in the absence of light. This dark or hot count results from the electrons' erratic movements inside the semiconductor. To produce an adequately calibrated image, the dark count must be eliminated.

It is possible to functionally split the raw dark count in a randomly selected pixel into a dark count (D) and a bias count (B).

$$D_{raw} = (D + B)_{raw}$$

$$N_{D,raw}^2 = N_D^2 + N_B^2$$

To get the true dark count, we must subtract a bias frame (B). To put it another way, the calibration frame needs to be "calibrated." It is possible to ascertain the corresponding signal and noise levels:

$$D_{cal} = (D + B)_{raw} - \hat{B}$$

$$N_{D,raw}^2 = N_D^2 + N_B^2 + N_{\hat{B}}^2$$

(Newberry, 1995)

After using DSLR cameras for some time, the temperature naturally rises. This leads to thermal noise, dark current, and hot pixels. Dark frames are used to eliminate them. Reducing dark frame errors is especially crucial for DSLR cameras, which can't control their temperature like scientific astronomical cameras. Dark frames are photographs taken with the same exposure time as light frames but in complete darkness. Astronomical CCDs can easily take dark frames by simply exposing without opening the shutter (Zhang et al., 2016). Since it is not possible to take pictures without opening the shutter in Canon EOS 6D Mark II, dark frames are taken using a different method.

Dark frames were captured with the lens cap on and the eyepiece covered, as shown in Figure 6, with the same ISO and exposure time settings as light frames. Since the Canon EOS 6D Mark II is used in this study, a consumer DSLR camera, the temperature of the light and dark frames could not be guaranteed to be exact. This was considered a limitation of the calibration process.

Figure 6. Camera Setup for Dark Frame Acquisition

2.3.1.2. Bias Frames

The bias count appears as a misleading signal in every image because it is brought on by the charge provided to a CCD to activate its photon-collecting capacity. The bias level usually fluctuates over time due to temperature changes in the camera's circuits. Therefore, the best estimate of bias is provided by measurements taken right after a picture is taken. A bias frame often consists of a structure where the average value of the pixels in one area of the image differs from that of the pixels in another. As a result, the raw bias count (B_{raw}) can be functionally divided into a bias structure (B_{struc}) that contains noise and a noise-free bias offset (B_{offset}). To make the notation clearer, B_{raw} , fluctuates from pixel to pixel, B_{struc} , varies from pixel to pixel, and B_{offset} , is a constant that is the same for all pixels.

$$B_{raw} = B_{offset} + B_{struc}$$

It turns out that although the bias offset may fluctuate over time, the bias structure remains remarkably stable. In order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio, it is advantageous for some processing to separate B_{struc} from B_{offset} and correct them independently. By computing the mean across a sufficiently large area, the proper bias offset can be easily obtained. When computing the mean, it is essential to constantly use the same area; otherwise, any bias structure would negatively impact the outcomes. (Newberry, 1995)

Another important noise to remove is the sensor's basic readout noise, which is unwanted electronic noise from the sensor, even when no light hits it. This can be removed by bias frames. Unlike scientific astronomical cameras, DSLR cameras cannot take zero-exposure frames, so for bias frames, the shortest exposure time is used. A similar setup with dark frames was also used for bias frames to avoid light hitting the sensor.

2.3.1.3. Flat Frames

The flat-field frame is the final frame required for picture calibration. A flat-field frame is a map of the relative sensitivity of each pixel in the detector. Flat-field calibration corrects for inconsistencies throughout the telescope's field of view and changes in the sensitivity of the CCD itself. They are produced by picturing a surface that is evenly lit. depicts a typical flat-field frame.

A randomly selected pixel's flat-field count can be functionally divided into three counts: bias (B), dark (D), and light signal (F).

$$F_{raw} = (F + D + B)_{raw}$$

$$N_{F,raw}^2 = N_F^2 + N_D^2 + N_B^2$$

The dark count (D) and bias count (B) must be eliminated in order to calibrate the flat-field frame. The subtraction raises the noise level once more because there is noise in both the bias count and the dark. It is possible to ascertain the corresponding signal and noise levels:

$$F_{cal} = (F + D + B)_{raw} - \hat{D} - \hat{B}$$

$$N_{F,cal}^2 = N_F^2 + N_D^2 + N_B^2 + N_D^2 + N_B^2$$

The average pixel value shouldn't change when divided by a flat-field frame. Normalizing the flat-field frame to an average pixel value of one count is therefore beneficial. This can be accomplished by dividing the flat field frame by its average flat-field count, or F. Following the flat-field frame's normalization to an average value of 1, the signal and noise levels are

$$S_{F,nrm} = \frac{F_{cal}}{F}$$

$$N_{F,nrm}^2 = \frac{N_{F,cal}^2}{F^2}$$

Since dividing or multiplying by a constant affects both the signal and the noise in the same way, the signal-to-noise ratio remains constant.

$$\frac{S_{F,nrm}}{N_{F,nrm}} = \frac{F_{cal}}{N_{F,cal}}$$

(Rest, 1996)

For the image acquisition, the camera should be aimed at a uniformly illuminated featureless target that will fill the field of view. Ideally, the resulting pictures will be uniformly bright, with a pixel-to-pixel variation that is a combination of the read noise, the Poisson statistics that govern the number of photoelectrons generated in each pixel, and a possible

fixed pattern noise arising from nonuniformity in the pixels' response to light (Owen Jr., 2024).

Similar to dark frames, flat fields also aid in normalizing the lights; however, the flaws they fix are caused by optical flaws in the DSLR cameras. DSLR cameras are unable to produce uniform lighting across the camera sensor. The visuals appear darker around the edges and brighter in the middle as a result. In astrophotography, this phenomenon, known as vignetting, occurs frequently. Additionally, dust particles on the optical path frequently result in "dust donuts," or blotches. To illustrate what continuous brightness should look like, flat fields are taken. To apply a master flat field to the light frames in the same manner as the master dark, they are then averaged. To ensure that the same conditions are met, flats must be photographed using the same focus, camera orientation, and optical setup as the lights. Flats can be taken in a variety of ways, including by directing the telescope at a white computer screen, using the evening sky, or using a light box. This is a result of the DSLR camera's optics and is independent of temperature or time between observations (Ireland, 2019).

In this paper, two different methods were used to take flat frames. The first one is a more commonly used method, which includes a completely white digital screen. As an alternative method, a closed box was prepared with evenly spaced white LEDs, and white paper was placed in front of the LEDs to ensure they were evenly lit and smooth.

Digital Screen Method: A surface as textureless and evenly bright as possible was achieved by using a monitor displaying a completely white screen. The camera was positioned in front of the monitor, directly facing the screen, at close range, mounted on a tripod. The desired number of flat frames was then acquired in a dark room, with the monitor as the only light source, using DigiCamControl.

Figure 7. The dust has been wiped off the screen.

To prevent any errors caused by dust on the screen, the screen is cleaned with a microfiber towel and screen-cleaning spray.

Figure 8. Flat Frame Acquisition Digital Screen Method

Flat Box Method: For this method, a special box was made to minimize outside light and to distribute the inside light as evenly as possible. The interior of the box was covered with white A4 paper. A separate panel with LED strips was built for the back of the box. A sheet of semi-transparent, parchment-like paper was placed a few centimeters in front of the LED panel to evenly distribute the light. In the front panel of the box, a hole for the camera's lens was cut. In this way, an environment was created that was closed on all four sides and distributed the internal light source as evenly as possible. The camera was placed at the hole using a

tripod, and the desired number of flat frames was taken with DigiCamControl.

First, a literature review was conducted on flat box manufacturing. It was concluded that this method has been less frequently attempted compared to other flat frame methods. Following the literature review, the flat box production was completed by following the steps below.

Figure 9. LEDs evenly placed on top of a plate.

Figure 10. Soldering and electrical connection of LEDs.

First, white LEDs were placed on a flat plate. Then, these LEDs were connected to the electrical wiring.

Figure 11. To evenly distribute the light, a thin tracing paper is used.

Figure 12. Inside the box is finalized.

Figure 13. A hole is opened as the size of the camera lens.

After that, the box has been manufactured as shown in figures 11,12 and 13.

Figure 14. Flat Frame Acquisition Flat Box Method

2.4 DeepSkyStacker

DeepSkyStacker is a software that processes astronomical images by stacking calibration frames and reducing noise errors. The main reason for its use in this study is that it is an open-source, free software.

At first, all the frames are added to the program. Then each frame is registered. The registration process detects stars in light frames. This will be used to align each light frame later. DSS (DeepSkyStacker) has detected nearly 34,000 stars in one light frame taken for the detection of (7) Iris. However, using nearly 34,000 detected stars for alignment would require too much processing power. So, during the registration star detection threshold is set as 3% to prevent the crashing of the program. The star number to align frames can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Register Settings

As the next step, the settings are adjusted for the stacking process as shown in Figures 16 and 17.

Figure 16. Intersection mode is used as stacking method.

Figure 17. Stacking Settings

For every calibration frame, the Median Kappa-Sigma clipping method is used with 5 number of iterations.

Using the settings shown, DSS converts all calibration frames into a master calibration frame. It then extracts these from the finalized light frame and creates a single file in FITS format. This FITS file is then ready to be sent to Astrometry.net for star detection and processing.

2.4.1. Generation of Master Calibration Frames

To reduce random noise in the calibration data, individual calibration frames were combined into master calibration frames. The bias frames were combined to create a master bias frame, while the dark frames were combined to create a master dark frame for each exposure and ISO setting. If flat-field frames were available, they were also combined and normalized to create a master flat frame.

Using master frames instead of single calibration images improves the stability of the correction process. Previous CCD calibration work also emphasizes the use of master bias, master dark, and master flat-field frames as a standard procedure for reducing repeatable sensor patterns and improving the quality of calibrated astronomical images (Rest, 1996).

2.4.2. Calibrated Science Frame Generation

After the acquisition of light and calibration frames, the raw science images were calibrated. First, the master bias and master dark components were subtracted from the raw light frame. Then, flat-field correction was applied if a master flat frame was available. The general calibration procedure can be represented as:

$$S_{cal} = \frac{S_{measured} - \hat{D} - \hat{B}}{\hat{F}}$$

(Rest, 1996)

Where S_{cal} is calibrated frames, $S_{measured}$ are raw light frames, and \hat{D} , \hat{B} and \hat{F} are the master frames.

2.5 Astrometric Calibration

A raw astronomical image contains no information about its location or orientation in the sky. Every pixel in the image directly corresponds to a certain location in the sky. This pixel-to-coordinate transformation must be found during astrometric calibration. Astrometric calibration determines the equations that relate pixel coordinates (where (x, y) defines the position of any point in the image) to celestial coordinates (where α is the right ascension and δ is the declination). The resulting parameters are encoded in the image file header as the World Coordinate System (WCS), describing the transformation from image coordinates to celestial coordinates (Lang et al., 2010). The most basic form of this map is a linear affine transform. An affine transform is a mathematical formula that applies a linear transformation to map coordinates between the images and the sky:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} CD_{11} & CD_{12} \\ CD_{12} & CD_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x - x_0 \\ y - y_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

(Lang et al., 2010)

Here (ξ, η) are intermediate projected coordinates in radians, (x_0, y_0) is the reference pixel, and the CD matrix encodes the plate scale -how much sky area each pixel represents- and the image's rotation on the sky. This linear model is suitable for narrow-field telescope images; however, lens distortion becomes considerable for wide-angle optics, such as consumer DSLR lenses, demanding higher-order correction terms. For wide-angle and all-sky systems, the standard linear WCS breaks down, and dedicated distortion models are required (Barghini et al., 2019).

The most general case, where nothing about the image's parameters, such as pointing, scale, or orientation, is known beforehand, is a direct instance of the classical "lost in space" problem (Lang et al., 2010)

2.5.1. Plate Solving

2.5.1.1. Blind Plate Solving: Astrometry.net

RAW images captured with commercial DSLR cameras suffer from irregular lighting or darkening due to temperature and electronic noise, affecting the optics and therefore not being ready for scientific analysis. These images are calibrated using master bias (Newberry, 1995a), master dark (Newberry, 1995b), and master flat frames (Newberry, 1996). The resulting RAW images provide clean images. After converting the RAW images to FITS format, their metadata (exposure time, ISO, focal length) is written to the FITS header section of the Astrometry.net application (Lang et al., 2010). Astrometry.net can be used as a web service or as a local installation. In this study, it is used locally. First, star candidates, or point sources, in the captured image are identified as the main bright points. Then, the pixel coordinates of each point source are extracted. The star pattern of the identified point sources is compared with the locally installed Tycho-2 catalog. Incorrectly matched patterns are eliminated to verify the star pattern match. The World Coordinate System parameters of the image, from which the point sources have been identified (i.e., the star pattern has been extracted), are calculated. Finally, these parameters are added to the FITS header, which has been calibrated on Astrometry.net.

Figure 18. Detected stars using Astrometry.net local.

Classical matching methods require a reasonable initial estimate of the image pointing, scale, and orientation. Astrometry.net requires none of that; it operates directly from pixel data alone (Lang et al., 2010). The algorithm proceeds in four steps:

1. **Source detection:** A few hundred stars are detected and localized to sub-pixel accuracy.

2. **Quad construction:** The detected sources form quads, groups of four stars. The ratios of inter-star

distances are employed to generate a geometric hash code that is invariant to scale, translation, and rotation for each quad.

3. **Index search:** The hash code is obtained from a precomputed index established from catalog stars. Each match yields a hypothesis about the image's pointing and scale.

4. **Bayesian verification:** Bayesian decision theory is used to compare each hypothesis to a null hypothesis. The first hypothesis that satisfies the confidence level is acknowledged as the solution. Lang reports a success rate of greater than 99.9% with USNO-B indices (Monet et al., 2003), achieving 100% accuracy without false positives when supplemented with 2MASS (Lang et al., 2010). Failures are caused by incomplete catalogs rather than by the algorithm itself.

2.5.1.2. Reference Catalog Matching

The fundamental approach to astrometric calibration involves matching stars detected in the image to a reference catalog of known celestial coordinates. Popular star catalogs are the USNO-B, 2MASS (Two Micron All Sky Survey), Tycho-2, and UCAC. Pier compared the accuracy of Tycho-2 and UCAC for Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) astrometry (Pier et al., 2003). They concluded that UCAC has better absolute accuracy than Tycho-2, with residuals of approximately 45 mas per coordinate compared to 75 mas per coordinate for Tycho-2. The general calibration process is: using an image to find sources, compute the pixel positions of their centroids; geometrically match the centroid listing to catalog positions; fit the scale and rotation parameters by least squares; and write out the WCS solution to the header of a FITS file (Lang et al., 2010).

2.5.2. Error Sources

2.5.2.1. Atmospheric Refraction

The atmosphere bends incoming light, thus a star's observed position is shifted from its true celestial coordinates. Pier identifies anomalous refraction as one of the dominant error sources in SDSS astrometry, noting that correlated components extending over angular scales of 2° or more on the sky cannot be easily removed (Pier et al., 2003). Along with random errors in reference databases, atmospheric refraction is one of the fundamental restrictions on astrometric precision.

2.5.2.2. Reference Catalog Accuracy

The accuracy of astrometric calibration depends on the reference catalog used. Pier quantifies this ceiling: with the UCAC catalog, the residual is approximately 45 mas per coordinate, while Tycho-2 yields 75 mas per coordinate (Pier et al., 2003). Both catalogs carry an additional 20-30 mas of systematic error, and for faint stars, photon noise can push centroid uncertainties to approximately 100 mas.

$$\sigma_{UCAC} \approx 45 \text{ mas rms per coordinate}$$

$$\sigma_{Tycho-2} \approx 75 \text{ mas rms per coordinate}$$

(Pier et al., 2003)

2.5.2.3. Centroid Errors

The pixel position of the star requires a precise measurement, even with a perfect reference database. According to the point spread function (PSF), stars' flux spreads across multiple pixels rather than on a single pixel. It is essential to locate the centroid, the intensity-weighted center of this distribution, using the surrounding brightness values. A systematic bias in centroid estimation is introduced by PSF asymmetry, and this bias directly affects the astrometric and navigation solutions (Pier et al., 2003; Yıldır, 2024a).

Predicted star positions in the images can be verified by projecting the catalog coordinates onto the target plane once a WCS solution has been established. The measured centroids and the projected positions can then be compared. This approach enables the iterative refinement of centroid calculations to minimize bias in star locations and improve final navigation accuracy (Pinto, 2022).

2.5.2.4. Lens Distortion

Lens distortion is another source of positional error introduced by consumer DSLR lenses. A star that should fall at a specific pixel position is shifted to a slightly different location due to the optical geometry of the lens. This effect is usually negligible for narrow-field telescopes, but for consumer lenses with broader fields of view, the displacement is significant enough to require explicit correction in the astrometric model (Barghini et al., 2019).

3. Results

Figure 19. Detected asteroid (7) Iris (Magnitude: 10.68) by the astrometric stacking program (ASTAP).

Detected ASTAP coordinates of (7) Iris:

RA: 10:13:58.9
Dec: +4 10' 31.8"

Real coordinates of (7) Iris based on the JPL Horizons system:

RA: 10:14:02.90
Dec: +4 09' 50.7"

Error calculation between expected (JPL Horizons) and measured (ASTAP) coordinates:

RA: 00:00:04 = 60"
Dec: +0 00' 41.1" = 41.1"

Total angular position error is approximately 72.6"

As can be seen from the error calculation, the detection of asteroid (7) Iris with the usage of Canon 6D Mark II shows us that it is possible to use that camera and sensor to calculate our position in space with a relatively small error.

3.1 Comparison Between the Flat Box Method and the Flat Screen Method

Calibrated images obtained using flats acquired with two methods are shown in Figures 20 and 21. As can be seen, they are quite different from each other.

When the screen method is used, the vignetting error is observed more. Also, due to the pixels of the screen, the output is not as clear as the other output that was calibrated using the box method. Besides, the image shows an over-enhanced red

channel, which may lead to detail loss in some bright regions.

On the other hand, the image calibrated with the box method shows less vignetting and clearer visuals. The smooth texture of the chosen paper prevents pixelation errors and results in a more accurate outcome.

Figure 20. Output calibrated with flats taken using the digital screen method.

Figure 21. Output calibrated with flats taken using the flat box method.

Figure 22. (7) Iris asteroid detected from the image calibrated using the flat box method.

After deciding that the flat box method was more suitable, the asteroid detection process was carried out using images calibrated with flat box frames. As can be seen from Figure 22, (7) Iris asteroid, which has a quite large magnitude for DSLR cameras, which is 10.68, is detected successfully.

4. Conclusion

This study investigates the feasibility of imaging with a commercial DSLR camera using autonomous optical navigation while keeping costs low.

DigiCamControl, which is an open-source software, was used to capture the image remotely and without creating vibration. The raw image was calibrated using Flat, Bias, and Dark Frames to reduce noise in the captured raw image. Flat Frame Digital Screen and Light Box methods have shown that calibration can be performed using inexpensive and readily available materials. The calibrated images were then stacked by using DeepSkyStacker (DSS), another open-source software used in this study. Astrometric plate solutions were also obtained using the Astrometry.net application.

As a result of these applied methods, asteroid (7) Iris {107} was detected. For the asteroid (7) Iris, the coordinates appear as "RA: 10:14:02.90" and "Dec: +4 09' 50.7" " in the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) Horizons system, while in the Astrometric Stacking Program (ASTAP) the coordinates are recorded as "RA: 10:13:58.9" and "Dec: +4 10' 31.8" ". There is an angular position error between these recorded reference coordinates. The angular position error was calculated as "RA: 00:00:04 = 60" " and "Dec: +0 00' 41.1" = 41.1" ", from which the total angular position error is approximately 72.6", which is a value that cannot be neglected. Nevertheless, it can be said that the Canon EOS 6D Mark II, which is a commercial DSLR camera, does a fairly good job of detecting objects in the inertial system. Thus, this study strongly supports the basic idea that it has confirmed the usability of a commercial camera for optical navigation on asteroid detection missions.

Finally, it has been proven that it is possible to build an autonomous optical navigation system at low cost using open-source software and a camera with commercial hardware. The next critical step is to expand the system from DigiCamControl to cFS Basecamp on a Raspberry Pi based system. The goal is to improve calibration despite changing conditions and to transform the system into a fully autonomous software architecture.

5. Next Step

To advance the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) (Mankins, 1995) of our demonstration, the process of image acquisition without human interference has been enhanced by a feasibility analysis of utilizing cFS Basecamp. cFS Basecamp is a lightweight environment designed as a framework for the NASA core Flight System (cFS) applications (McComas and Tandy, 2023). cFS Basecamp runs on Linux, and its lightweight structure enables running the application on microcontrollers, such as the Raspberry Pi family. This transition from DigiCamControl to cFS Basecamp simplifies the camera control by replacing the computer with a microcontroller.

The next development stage involves creating a cFS application that manages autonomous image capture, running on a Raspberry Pi as the flight computer substitute. A cFS application registers with the cFS scheduler, publishes and subscribes to messages over the internal software bus (SB) and responds to timed events or commands, all of which are prerequisites for a system that must eventually operate autonomously on a spacecraft (McComas and Tandy, 2023). To connect cFS with the external Python script, the JSON Message (JMSG) facility is used. JMSG monitors the SB for outgoing messages and translates them into JSON packets that non-cFS programs, such as the Python script, can consume.

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Figure 23. Autonomous Image Capture Flow

With this improvement, the foundations of physical implementation are laid. Future studies may include hardware-in-the-loop ground experiments of the SmallSat with a microcontroller simulating the flight computer.

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